

Optimal Defender Strategies for CAGE-2 using Causal Modeling and Tree Search *Supplementary Material*

Author names withheld for double-blind reviewing.

APPENDIX A

PROOF OF PARTICLE FILTER CONVERGENCE

1) CASE: $t = 1$.

PROOF: \mathbf{b}_1 is given, hence $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_1 = \mathbf{b}_1$.

2) CASE: $t > 1$.

PROOF: Assume $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{t-1} = \mathbf{b}_{t-1}$ and let

$$g(\bar{\sigma}_t) \triangleq \sum_{\sigma_{t-1}} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_{t-1}(\sigma_{t-1}) P(\bar{\sigma} | \sigma_{t-1}, \text{do}(\mathbf{X}'_{t-1} = \mathbf{x}'_{t-1})).$$

We then have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{b}_t(\sigma) &= \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\sigma} \sim \mathbf{b}_t} [\delta_{\sigma, \bar{\sigma}}] = \sum_{\bar{\sigma}} \mathbf{b}_t(\bar{\sigma}) \delta_{\sigma, \bar{\sigma}} \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \sum_{\bar{\sigma}} \frac{g(\bar{\sigma})}{g(\sigma)} \mathbf{b}_t(\bar{\sigma}) \delta_{\sigma, \bar{\sigma}} = \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\sigma} \sim g} \left[\frac{\mathbf{b}_t(\bar{\sigma})}{g(\bar{\sigma})} \delta_{\sigma, \bar{\sigma}} \right] \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{=} \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\sigma} \sim g} \left[\frac{\eta P(\mathbf{o}_t | \sigma_t) g(\bar{\sigma})}{g(\bar{\sigma})} \delta_{\sigma, \bar{\sigma}} \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{\bar{\sigma} \sim g} [\eta P(\mathbf{o}_t | \sigma_t) \delta_{\sigma, \bar{\sigma}}], \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where (b) follows from the definition of \mathbf{b} . As $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{t-1} = \mathbf{b}_{t-1}$, the denominator in (a) is non-zero for all $\bar{\sigma}$ where $\mathbf{b}_t(\bar{\sigma}) > 0$. Since the particles are distributed according to $\eta' \eta P(\mathbf{o}_t | \sigma_t) g(\bar{\sigma}_t)$ (η' is a normalizing factor), it follows from the strong law of large numbers [1, Thm. 6.2] that $\hat{\mathbf{b}}(\sigma_t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \delta_{\sigma_t, \hat{\sigma}_t^{(i)}}$ converges P -almost surely to (1) as $M \rightarrow \infty$. (Remark: the probability measure P in (1) exists since $|\text{dom}(\Sigma_t) \cup \text{dom}(\mathbf{O}_t)| < \infty$ (Thm. 1, [2, Thm. 2.2.1]).) \square

APPENDIX B

PROOF OF THEOREM 3

It follows from Appendix A and [3, Lem. 1–2] that C-POMCP corresponds to the UCT algorithm [4, Fig. 1] when $M \rightarrow \infty$. Hence, we can base the proof of convergence of C-POMCP when $M \rightarrow \infty$ on the proof of convergence for UCT, which is originally published in [4]. The key insight behind the proof is that the decision problem at each node in the search tree of C-POMCP corresponds to a non-stationary multi-armed bandit problem (MAB), which becomes stationary if the prescribed actions at the child nodes converge. Further, the tree policy corresponds to the UCB1 bandit algorithm [5, Fig. 1]. As a consequence, it suffices to prove that UCB1 converges at each node in the search tree. Towards this proof, we state and prove the following six lemmas.

Notation. $K = \mathcal{O}(|2^{\mathbf{X}_t}|)$ is the number of arms in the MAB at each node in the search tree; t indexes the MAB rounds; $R_{i,t}$ is the reward of arm i at round t ; $\bar{R}_{i,n} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n R_{i,n}$ is the mean reward of arm i based on n samples; $\mu_{i,n}$ is the mean of $\bar{R}_{i,n}$; $\mu_i \triangleq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu_{i,n}$; $\mu_i \triangleq \mu_{i,n} - \delta_{i,n}$; $T_i(t)$ is the number of times arm i has been pulled at round t ; $\Delta_i \triangleq \mu^* - \mu_i$; I_t is the arm picked at round t ; and $c_{t,n}$ is the exploration term in UCB1 for an arm that has been pulled n times at round t . Quantities related to the optimal arm are superscripted by \star , i.e., $\mu^*, T^*(t)$, etc.

Assumption 1 (Bounded rewards and asymptotic stationarity).

- 1) $R_{i,n} \in [0, 1]$ for all i and n .
- 2) The limit $\mu_i = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_{i,t}$ exists for each arm i .
- 3) There exists a constant C_p and an integer N_p such that for $n \geq N_p$ and any $\delta \geq 0$, the following bounds hold.

$$\begin{aligned} P(n\bar{R}_{i,n} \geq n\mu_{i,n} + C_p \sqrt{n \ln(1/\delta)}) &\leq \delta \\ P(n\bar{R}_{i,n} \geq n\mu_{i,n} - C_p \sqrt{n \ln(1/\delta)}) &\leq \delta. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 1. Given Assumption 1, if $c_{t,n} = 2C_p \sqrt{\frac{\ln t}{n}}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P(\bar{R}_{i,n} \geq \mu_{i,n} + c_{t,n}) &\leq t^{-4} & n \geq N_p \\ P(\bar{R}_{i,n} \geq \mu_{i,n} - c_{t,n}) &\leq t^{-4} & n \geq N_p. \end{aligned}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} P(n\bar{R}_{i,n} \geq n\mu_{i,n} + C_p \sqrt{n \ln(1/\delta)}) &\stackrel{(\text{Assumption 1})}{\leq} \delta \\ \implies P(\bar{R}_{i,n} \geq \mu_{i,n} + C_p \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{n}}) &\geq \delta \\ \stackrel{(\delta=t^{-4})}{\implies} P(\bar{R}_{i,n} \geq \mu_{i,n} + 2C_p \sqrt{\frac{\ln(t)}{n}}) &\geq t^{-4}. \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Lemma 2. If Assumption 1 holds, then there exists an integer $N_0(\epsilon)$ such that $t \geq N_0(\epsilon) \implies |\delta_{i,t}| \leq \frac{\epsilon \Delta_i}{2}$ and $|\delta_{j^*,t}| \leq \min_i \frac{\epsilon \Delta_i}{2}$ for all $\epsilon > 0$.

Proof. Consequence of Assumption 1. \square

Lemma 3. Given Assumption 1, if the exploration term used by UCB1 [5, Fig. 1] is $c_{t,s} = 2C_p \sqrt{\frac{\ln t}{s}}$, then

$$\mathbb{E}[T_i(t)] \leq \frac{16C_p^2 \ln t}{(1-\epsilon)^2 \Delta_i^2} + N_0(\epsilon) + N_p + 1 + \frac{\pi^2}{3} \quad (2)$$

for all $\epsilon > 0$ and each sub-optimal arm i .

Proof. Let $A_0(t, \epsilon) \triangleq \min[s \mid c_{t,s} \leq (1 - \epsilon)\Delta_i/2]$ and $A(t, \epsilon) \triangleq \max[A_0(t, \epsilon), N_0(\epsilon), N_p]$. Next note that

$$\begin{aligned} c_{t,s} \leq (1 - \epsilon)\Delta_i/2 &\implies 2C_p \sqrt{\frac{\ln t}{s}} \leq (1 - \epsilon)\Delta_i/2 \\ \implies 16C_p \frac{\ln t}{s} &\leq (1 - \epsilon)^2 \Delta_i^2 \implies s \geq \frac{16C_p \ln t}{(1 - \epsilon)^2 \Delta_i^2} \\ \implies A_0(t, \epsilon) &= \left\lceil \frac{16C_p \ln t}{(1 - \epsilon)^2 \Delta_i^2} \right\rceil. \end{aligned}$$

Now consider $T_i(n)$. By definition:

$$\begin{aligned} T_i(n) &= 1 + \sum_{t=K+1}^n \mathbb{1}\{I_t = i\} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{t=K+1}^n \mathbb{1}\{I_t = i, T_i(t-1) \geq A(n, \epsilon)\} + \\ &\quad \sum_{t=K+1}^n \mathbb{1}\{I_t = i, T_i(t-1) < A(n, \epsilon)\} \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{\leq} A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=K+1}^n \mathbb{1}\{I_t = i, T_i(t-1) \geq A(n, \epsilon)\} \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{\leq} A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=K+1}^n \mathbb{1}\left\{ \bar{R}_{T^*(t-1)}^* + c_{t-1, T^*(t-1)} \leq \right. \\ &\quad \left. \bar{R}_{i, T_i(t-1)} + c_{t-1, T_i(t-1)}, T_i(t-1) \geq A(n, \epsilon) \right\} \\ &\leq A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=K+1}^n \mathbb{1}\left\{ \min_{0 < s < t} \bar{R}_s^* + c_{t-1, s} \leq \right. \\ &\quad \left. \max_{A(n, \epsilon) < s_i < t} \bar{R}_{i, s_i} + c_{t-1, s_i} \right\} \\ &\leq A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=K+1}^n \sum_{s=1}^{t-1} \sum_{s_i=A(n, \epsilon)}^{t-1} \mathbb{1}\left\{ \bar{R}_s^* + c_{t-1, s} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \leq \bar{R}_{i, s_i} + c_{t-1, s_i} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where (a) follows because the second sum is upper bounded by $n - K$ and $n < A(n, \epsilon) \implies T_i(n) < A(n, \epsilon)$. (b) follows from the arm-selection rule in UCB1 [5, Fig. 1].

Next note that for $t \geq A(n, \epsilon) \geq N_0(\epsilon)$, we have $\mu_t^* \geq \mu_{i,t} + 2c_{t,s_i}$. This inequality holds because

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_t^* \geq \mu_{i,t} + 2c_{t,s_i} &\iff \mu_t^* - \mu_{i,t} - 4C_p \sqrt{\frac{\ln t}{s_i}} \geq 0 \\ &\stackrel{(t \geq A_0(n, \epsilon))}{\iff} \mu_t^* - \mu_{i,t} - (1 - \epsilon)\Delta_i \geq 0 \\ &\iff \mu_t^* + \delta^* - \mu_{i,t} - \delta_{i,t} - (1 - \epsilon)\Delta_i \geq 0 \\ &\stackrel{(\text{Lemma 2})}{\iff} \mu_t^* - \epsilon\Delta_i - \mu_{i,t} - (1 - \epsilon)\Delta_i \geq 0 \\ &\iff \mu_t^* - \mu_{i,t} - \Delta_i \geq 0 \iff \Delta_i - \Delta_i \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Using the above inequality we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} P(\bar{R}_s^* + c_{t-1, s} \leq \bar{R}_{i, s_i} + c_{t-1, s_i}) &\leq \\ P(\bar{R}_s^* \leq \mu_t^* + c_{t,s}) + P(\bar{X}_{i, s_i} \geq \mu_{i,t} + c_{t, s_i}). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

This follows because if the left inequality above holds and the right inequalities do not hold, we obtain

$$\bar{R}_s^* + c_{t-1, s} \leq \bar{R}_{i, s_i} + c_{t-1, s_i}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \implies \mu_t^* - c_{t,s} + c_{t-1, s} &< \mu_{i,t} + c_{t, s_i} + c_{t-1, s_i} \\ \implies \mu_t^* &< \mu_{i,t} + 2c_{t, s_i}, \end{aligned}$$

which by (4) is false for $t \geq A(n, \epsilon) \geq N_0(\epsilon)$. Now we take expectations of both sides of the inequality in (3) and plug in (5), which gives

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[T_i(n)] &\leq A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=K+1}^n \sum_{s=1}^{t-1} \sum_{s_i=A(n, \epsilon)}^{t-1} P(\bar{R}_s^* \leq \mu_t^* + c_{t,s}) \\ &\quad + P(\bar{X}_{i, s_i} \geq \mu_{i,t} + c_{t, s_i}) \\ &\stackrel{(\text{Lemma 1})}{\leq} A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=K+1}^n \sum_{s=1}^{t-1} \sum_{s_i=A(n, \epsilon)}^{t-1} 2t^{-4} \\ &\leq A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \sum_{s=1}^t \sum_{s_i=1}^t 2t^{-4} \\ &= A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} t^{-2} + t^{-3} \leq A(n, \epsilon) + \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} t^{-2} + \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} t^{-2} \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} A(n, \epsilon) + \frac{\pi^2}{3} \leq \frac{16C_p \ln t}{(1 - \epsilon)^2 \Delta_i^2} + 1 + N_0(\epsilon) + N_p + \frac{\pi^2}{3}, \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows from the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(2) = \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} t^{-2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$. \square

Lemma 4 (Lower bound). *Given Assumption 1, there exists a positive constant ρ such that for all i and t , $T_i(t) \geq \lceil \rho \log t \rceil$.*

Proof. Since $R_{i,t} \in [0, 1]$ and $T_i(t-1) \geq 1$ for all $t \geq K$, there exists a constant M such that

$$\mu_{i,t} + 2C_p \sqrt{\frac{\ln t}{T_i(t-1)}} \leq M \quad (6)$$

$$\implies T_i(t-1) \geq \frac{4C^2 \ln t}{(M - \mu_i - \delta_{i,t})^2} \quad (7)$$

for all i and $K \leq t < \infty$. Next note that Assumption 1 implies that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \delta_{i,t} = 0$, which means that there exists a constant $\rho \geq \frac{4C^2}{(M - \mu_i - \delta_{i,t})^2}$. Hence $T_i(t) \geq \lceil \rho \log t \rceil$. \square

Lemma 5. *Let $\bar{R}_n = \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{T_i(n)}{n} \bar{X}_{i, T_i(n)}$ and $N_0 = N_0(\epsilon = \frac{1}{2})$. Then the following holds under Assumption 1.*

$$|\mathbb{E}[\bar{R}_n] - \mu^*| \leq |\delta_n^*| + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{K(C_p^2 \ln n + N_0)}{n}\right).$$

Proof. By the triangle inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{E}[\bar{R}_n] - \mu^*| &\leq |\mu^* - \mu_n^*| + |\mu_n^* - \mathbb{E}[\bar{R}_n]| \\ &= |\delta_n^*| + |\mu_n^* - \mathbb{E}[\bar{X}_n]|. \end{aligned}$$

Hence it only remains to bound $|\mu_n^* - \mathbb{E}[\bar{X}_n]|$. By definition:

$$|\mu_n^* - \mathbb{E}[\bar{X}_n]| = \left| \mu_n^* - \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{i=1}^K \frac{T_i(n) \bar{R}_{i, T_i(n)}}{n}\right] \right| \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \implies n|\mu_n^* - \mathbb{E}[\bar{X}_n]| &= \left| \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{E}[R_i^*] - \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{i=1}^K T_i(n) \bar{R}_{i, T_i(n)}\right] \right| \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \left| \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{E}[R_i^*] - \mathbb{E}\left[T^*(n) \bar{R}_{T^*(n)}^*\right] \right| - \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{i \neq i^*} T_i(n) \bar{R}_{i, T_i(n)}\right], \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows because $\bar{R}_{i,t} \in [0,1]$ for all i and t (Assumption 1). We start by bounding the second term in (8):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i \neq i^*} T_i(n) \bar{R}_{i,T_i(n)} \right] &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i \neq i^*} T_i(n) \right] \\ &\stackrel{\text{(Lemma 3)}}{\leq} K \left(\frac{16C_p^2 \ln t}{(1-\epsilon)^2 \Delta_i^2} + N_0(\epsilon) + N_p + 1 + \frac{\pi^2}{3} \right) \\ &= \mathcal{O} \left(K (C_p^2 \ln n + N_0(\epsilon)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Now we consider the first term in (8). Note that $T^*(n) \bar{R}_{T^*(n)}^* = \frac{T^*(n)}{T^*(n)} \sum_{t=1}^{T^*(n)} \bar{R}_t^* = \sum_{t=1}^{T^*(n)} \bar{R}_t^*$. Using this expression we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{t=1}^n \mathbb{E}[R_t^*] - \mathbb{E} \left[T^*(n) \bar{R}_{T^*(n)}^* \right] \right| &= \left| \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=1}^n R_t^* - \sum_{t=1}^{T^*(n)} R_t^* \right] \right| \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \sum_{t=T^*(n)+1}^n \mathbb{E}[R_t^*] \leq \mathbb{E}[n - T^*(n)] = \sum_{i \neq i^*} \mathbb{E}[T_i(n)] \\ &\stackrel{\text{(Lemma 3)}}{\leq} K \left(\frac{16C_p^2 \ln t}{(1-\epsilon)^2 \Delta_i^2} + N_0(\epsilon) + N_p + 1 + \frac{\pi^2}{3} \right) \\ &= \mathcal{O} \left(K (C_p^2 \ln n + N_0(\epsilon)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows from the fact that $\bar{R}_{i,t} \in [0,1]$ for all i and t (Assumption 1). \square

Lemma 6. *Let n_0 be such that $\sqrt{n_0} \geq \mathcal{O}(K(C_p^2 \ln n_0 + N_0(\frac{1}{2})))$. Given Assumption 1, the following holds for any $n \geq n_0$ and $\delta > 0$:*

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(n \bar{X}_n \geq n \mathbb{E}[\bar{X}_n] + \mathfrak{A} \sqrt{2 \ln(2/\delta)} \right) &\leq \delta \\ P \left(n \bar{X}_n \geq n \mathbb{E}[\bar{X}_n] - \mathfrak{A} \sqrt{2 \ln(2/\delta)} \right) &\leq \delta \end{aligned}$$

Proof. This lemma was originally proved by Kocsis & Szepesvári [4, Thm. 5]. A more accessible version of the proof can be found in [6, Thm. 5]. For brevity we omit it here. \square

Lemma 7. *Given Assumption 1, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} P(I_t \neq i^*) = 0$.*

Proof. Let $p_{i,t} = P(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} \geq \bar{R}_{T^*(t)}^*)$. Clearly, $P(I_t \neq i^*) \leq \sum_{i \neq i^*} p_{i,t}$. Hence it suffices to show that $p_{i,t} \leq \frac{\epsilon}{K}$ for all i and any $\epsilon > 0$. Towards this proof, note that if $\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_i + \frac{\Delta_i}{2}$ and $\bar{R}_{T^*(t)}^* > \mu^* - \frac{\Delta_i}{2}$, then

$$\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_i + \frac{\Delta_i}{2} = \mu^* - \frac{\Delta_i}{2} < \bar{R}_{T^*(t)}^*.$$

As a consequence,

$$p_{i,t} \leq P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_i + \frac{\Delta_i}{2} \right) + P \left(\bar{R}_{T^*(t)}^* > \mu^* - \frac{\Delta_i}{2} \right).$$

Since $T_i(t)$ grows slower than $T^*(t)$, it suffices to bound the first of the two terms above. By definition:

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_i + \frac{\Delta_i}{2} \right) \\ = P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_{i,T_i(t)} - |\delta_{i,T_i(t)}| + \frac{\Delta_i}{2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Next note that $|\delta_{i,T_i(t)}|$ converges to 0 by Assumption 1. Hence we can assume that $|\delta_{i,T_i(t)}|$ is decreasing in t without loss

of generality. It then follows from Lemma 4 that $|\delta_{i,T_i(t)}| \leq |\delta_{i,\lceil \rho \log t \rceil}|$. Now consider $t \geq \lceil \rho \log t \rceil \geq N_0(\frac{\Delta_i}{4})$, then $|\delta_{i,T_i(t)}| \leq |\delta_{i,\lceil \rho \log t \rceil}| \leq \frac{\Delta_i}{4}$ by Lemma 2. As a consequence,

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_{i,T_i(t)} - |\delta_{i,T_i(t)}| + \frac{\Delta_i}{2} \right) \\ \leq P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_{i,T_i(t)} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4} \right) \\ \leq P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_{i,T_i(t)} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4}, T_i(t) \geq a \right) + P(T_i(t) \leq a). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Since $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} T_i(t) = \infty$ (Lemma 4), we have that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} P(T_i(t) < a) = 0$ for any a . Hence it suffices to bound the first term in (9), which can be done as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_{i,T_i(t)} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4}, T_i(t) \geq a \right) &\leq \\ P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_{i,T_i(t)} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4} \mid T_i(t) \in [a, b] \right) &P(T_i(t) \in [a, b]) \\ + P(T_i(t) \notin [a, b]). \end{aligned}$$

Next note that

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(\bar{R}_{i,T_i(t)} < \mu_{i,T_i(t)} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4} \mid T_i(t) \in [a, b] \right) \\ \leq \sum_{k=a}^b P \left(\bar{R}_{i,k} < \mu_{i,k} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4} \right) \\ \leq (b-a+1) \max_{a \leq k \leq b} P \left(\bar{R}_{i,k} < \mu_{i,k} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Now we use Assumption 1, which implies that the value of a in the expression above can be chosen such that for all $t \geq a$, $(t+1)P(\bar{X}_{i,t} \geq \mu_{i,t} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4}) < \frac{\epsilon}{2K}$, which means that

$$\begin{aligned} (b-a+1) \max_{a \leq k \leq b} P \left(\bar{R}_{i,k} < \mu_{i,k} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4} \right) \\ =^{b=2a} (a+1) \max_{a \leq k \leq b} P \left(\bar{R}_{i,k} < \mu_{i,k} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4} \right) \\ \leq (a+1) P \left(\bar{R}_{i,a} < \mu_{i,a} + \frac{\Delta_i}{4} \right) \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2K}. \end{aligned}$$

Putting the bounds above together, we get:

$$P(I_t \neq i^*) \leq \sum_{i \neq i^*} p_{i,t} \leq K \frac{\epsilon}{K} = \epsilon. \quad \square$$

Now we use Lemmas 1–7 to prove Thm. 3.

A. Proof of Theorem 3

The proof uses mathematical induction on the time horizon T , which corresponds to the depth of the search tree. Without loss of generality we assume that the target variables are normalized to the interval $[0,1]$.

For the inductive base case $T = 1$, C-POMCP corresponds to a stationary MAB problem, which means that Assumption 1.1–2 hold. Further, Assumption 1.3 follows from Hoeffding's inequality:

$$P \left(\bar{R}_{i,n} \leq \mu_{i,n} \pm \frac{1}{n} \sqrt{\frac{2 \ln t}{n}} \right) \leq e^{-2 \sqrt{\frac{2 \ln t}{n}}} = e^{-4 \ln t} = t^{-4}.$$

As a consequence, we can invoke Lemma 5 and Lemma 7, which asserts that the theorem statement holds when $T = 1$.

Assume by induction that the theorem statement holds for time horizons $2, 3, \dots, T-1$ and consider time horizon T . By Appendix A, the problem of finding an optimal intervention from the root node when the horizon is T corresponds to a non-stationary MAB with correlated rewards. This MAB satisfies Assumption 1.1 if the rewards are divided by T . Further it follows from the induction hypothesis that the reward distributions in each subtree converges, which means that Assumption 1.2 holds. Moreover, the induction hypothesis together with Lemma 6 implies that Assumption 1.3 is satisfied. As a consequence, we can apply Lemma 7 which ensures that the intervention prescribed at the root converges to an optimal intervention. Similarly, we can apply Lemma 5, which states that

$$|\mathbb{E}[\bar{R}_n - \mu_n^*]| \leq |\delta^*| + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{KC_p^2 \ln n + N_0}{n}\right),$$

where \bar{R}_n is the average reward at the root. By the induction hypothesis,

$$|\delta^*| = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{K(T-1) \log n + K^{T-1}}{n}\right).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{E}[\bar{R}_n - \mu_n^*]| &\leq \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{K(T-1) \log n + K^{T-1}}{n}\right) \\ &\quad + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{KC_p^2 \ln n + N_0}{n}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus it only remains to bound N_0 . It follows from Lemma 2 that N_0 is upper bounded by the smallest value of n for which the following inequality holds

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{K(T-1) \log n + K^{T-1}}{n} &\geq \frac{\Delta_i}{2} \\ \implies \frac{2(K^{T-1} + K(T-1) \log n)}{\Delta_i} &\geq n \implies N_0 = \mathcal{O}(K^{T-1}). \end{aligned}$$

As a consequence,

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{E}[\bar{R}_n - \mu_n^*]| &\leq \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{K(T-1) \log n + K^{T-1}}{n}\right) \quad (10) \\ &\quad + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{KC_p^2 \ln n + K^T}{n}\right) = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{(KT \log n + K^T)}{n}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by induction, the theorem holds for all T . \square

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Çinlar, *Probability and Stochastics*, ser. Graduate Texts in Mathematics. Springer New York, 2011.
- [2] J. S. Rosenthal, *A first look at rigorous probability theory*, 2nd ed. World Scientific Publishing Co. Pte. Ltd., Hackensack, NJ, 2006.
- [3] D. Silver and J. Veness, "Monte-carlo planning in large pomdps," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, J. Lafferty, C. Williams, J. Shawe-Taylor, R. Zemel, and A. Culotta, Eds., vol. 23. Curran Associates, Inc., 2010. [Online]. Available: https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2010/file/edfbe1afc9246bb0d40eb4d8027d90f-Paper.pdf

- [4] L. Kocsis and C. Szepesvári, "Bandit based monte-carlo planning," in *ECML*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, J. Fürnkranz, T. Scheffer, and M. Spiliopoulou, Eds., vol. 4212. Springer, 2006, pp. 282–293. [Online]. Available: <http://dblp.uni-trier.de/db/conf/ecml/ecml2006.html#KocsisS06>
- [5] P. Auer, N. Cesa-Bianchi, and P. Fischer, "Finite-time analysis of the multiarmed bandit problem," *Machine Learning*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 235–256, May 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1013689704352>
- [6] T. Dam, P. Klink, C. D'Eramo, J. Peters, and J. Pajarinen, "Generalized mean estimation in monte-carlo tree search," in *Proceedings of the Twenty-Ninth International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, ser. IJCAI'20, 2021.